

Solid State Ion-Exchange Properties of Antimonic Acid: Kinetics and Thermodynamics of Li-H Exchange

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The kinetics and thermodynamics of Li-H exchange on antimonic acid in solid state have been studied. The exchange takes place in two steps and the rate of exchange increases with temperature. The values of diffusion coefficients are comparable to those for exchange on cancrinite in solution. The values of activation energy for diffusion are lower than those for atomic diffusion in metals and for exchange on zeolites in solution. The effect of particle size of antimonic acid, concentration of LiCl and foreign salts, NaCl, KCl, AgCl, BaCl₂, MnCl₂, Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, Na₃PO₄, Na₄SiO₄, on Li-H exchange has been studied. Li⁺ is separated from its minerals on antimonic acid in solid state.

CRYSTALLINE antimonic acid is known to be an excellent cation exchanger¹⁻³. The ion-exchange mechanism of this compound has not been studied thoroughly. Contradictory statements about its structure and its different affinities for metal ions have been reported⁴⁻⁹. An attempt has been made here to study the kinetics and thermodynamics of Li-H exchange on crystalline antimonic acid in solid state. The effects of foreign salts, particle size of antimonic acid and LiCl concentration have been described.

Experimental

Antimonic acid was prepared⁵ from SbCl₃ (Albright and Wilson).

Ion-exchange between solids: A round bottom flask (250 ml) with an air inlet was connected to a spiral condenser through B-24 joints. The lower end of the condenser was dipped into a beaker containing NaOH solution. Antimonic acid was mixed with a salt and transferred into the flask. The flask was kept in a sand bath at the required temperature. Air was blown continuously into the reaction vessel and the HCl was transferred to the beaker containing NaOH. The content of the beaker were titrated to estimate the acid liberated due to the ion exchange. The radii of fine particles were determined by Cooke's research binocular microscope.

To study the effect of foreign salts on Li-H exchange, antimonic acid (0.5 g) and LiCl (0.1 g) were mixed with varying amounts (0.0-1.0 g) of the foreign salts. In order to determine the ion-exchange capacity antimonic acid (2.0 g) was mixed with LiCl (2.0 g) and the acid liberated in 2 h was collected. The mixture was then taken out, ground in a mortar, placed in the flask and the acid liberated was collected again. The cycle was repeated and

the total acid liberated in 6 h was titrated. The effect of particle size was studied by taking antimonic acid of different size (0.5 g, 100-200, 50-100 and 50 mesh) with powdered LiCl (0.2 g). LiCl was taken in varying quantities (0.0-3.0 g) with antimonic acid (1.0 g) for studying the Li⁺ concentration effect on Li-H exchange.

Results and Discussion

TG analysis showed the presence of 4H₂O per Sb₂O₅ unit⁶. The radii of the exchanger particles were found to be 0.5-0.75 μ. The exchanger (1.0 g) was heated (338-548 K) for 3 h with metal salt (1.0 g of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, AgCl, CuCl, Hg₂Cl₂, HgCl₂, CaCl₂, BaCl₂ and MnCl₂) to follow the ion-exchange. The amount of acid liberated was considerable in the case of LiCl while it was negligible in the case of remaining salts. The plot of ion-exchange capacity (K, acid liberated in meq/g of

Fig. 1. Ion-exchange capacity for Li as a function of temperature on antimonic acid.

antimonic acid) as a function of temperature is shown in Fig. 1. The value of K for Li-H exchange on antimonic acid is $8 \times 10^{-8} \text{ meq g}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Plots of fractional exchange, F as function of time (t) are shown in Fig. 2. F is defined as

$$F = \frac{\text{the amount of exchange at time } t}{\text{the amount of exchange at infinite time}}$$

Fig. 2. F as a function of time for Li-exchange on antimonic acid.

As the particle diffusion is the rate controlling step, the theory for particle diffusion⁷ can be applied. The fractional exchange, F , at time, t , for particle of radius, r , is given by the expression⁷

$$F = 1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \exp(-n^2 Bt), \text{ where } B = \frac{\pi^2 D_i}{r^2}$$

D_i is the effective diffusion coefficient of Li^+ and H^+ within the exchanger. The values of Bt as a function of F have been tabulated⁸. If the exchange is particle diffusion controlled and D_i is independent of F , a plot of Bt vs. t is a straight line passing

through the origin. Its slope will be B and if the particle radius is known, the value of D_i may be calculated. The resulting plots shown in Fig. 3 indicate that exchange takes place in two steps. Both the steps are independent of the concentration of ingoing ions (Li^+) and are particle-diffusion controlled. The slope for both the steps increases as the temperature increases and thus the rate of exchange increases with temperature. It is interesting to note that at 338 K the ion-exchange takes place in one step because the slope for the second step is zero; at 388 and 448 K ion-exchange takes place in two steps, an initial fast followed by a slow one, at 548 K ion-exchange takes place in two steps, an initial slow followed by a fast one. These facts suggest the existence of two different hydrogen atoms available for ion-exchange within the crystalline antimonic acid. This conclusion finds support from the reported work⁹ on crystalline antimonic acid in solution state.

The values of D_i (Table 1) were calculated from the data of Fig. 3. D_i follows the equation¹⁰

$$D_i = D_0 \exp(-Q/RT)$$

TABLE 1—DIFFUSION DATA OF THE Li^+ IN CRYSTALLINE ANTIMONIC ACID

Temp. K		D_i $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$	D_0 $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$	Q cal mol^{-1}
338	Step I	0.13×10^{-14}	1.3×10^{-9}	4700
	Step II	0	8.4×10^{-7}	6600
388	Step I	12×10^{-14}	—	—
	Step II	0.31×10^{-14}	—	—
448	Step I	18×10^{-14}	—	—
	Step II	1.83×10^{-14}	—	—
548	Step I	19×10^{-14}	—	—
	Step II	70×10^{-14}	—	—

where D_0 is a constant, Q is the activation energy for diffusion, R is the constant ($1.987 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and T is the temperature in K. The values of

Fig. 3. Bt as a function of time for Li-exchange on antimonic acid.

Q and D_0 were calculated from the plots of $\log D_t$ vs. $1000/K$. The values for the diffusion coefficient in crystalline antimonite are much lower than those for organic resins, thorium dioxide and crystalline zirconium phosphate in solution state^{7,8,10,11}. But these values are comparable in magnitude to those of basic cancrinite. Q is lower than that for atomic diffusion in metals¹² and ion-exchange in zeolites. They are comparable to those for the exchange in phenol sulphonic acid resins¹⁰.

Thermodynamics: The effect of LiCl concentration, particle size of antimonite and foreign salts on Li-H exchange is shown in Fig. 4 and 6. At 548 K

Fig. 4. Effect of LiCl concentration on Li-H exchange on antimonite.

the ion-exchange capacity of antimonite for Li^+ was found to be 2.87 meq g^{-1} . Ion-exchange isotherms are shown in Fig. 5. The reported procedure was used to compute the thermodynamic parameters⁸. The values are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 5. Isotherms of Li-H exchange on antimonite.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR THE Li-H EXCHANGE ON ANTIMONITE

Temp. K	ΔG° kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	k	ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
378	0.323	-1.540	0.655	-0.86
448	0.664		0.478	-1.49

Fig. 4 indicates that the exchange of Li increases first and then becomes constant on increasing the concentration of LiCl. Exchange isotherms resembled to those reported⁹ for Na-H, Ca-H and Sr-H exchange on antimonite in liquid state. It is clear from Fig. 6 that Li-H exchange occurs in presence of foreign salts. In case of Na_3PO_4 and Na_4SiO_4 the amount of acid liberated decreases sharply. It is due to the fact that H^+ produced by Li-H exchange reacts to give H_3PO_4 and H_4SiO_4 and since the boiling point ($\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4=213^\circ$) and ionisation constants (H_3PO_4 , $k_1=7.5 \times 10^{-8}$, $k_2=6.2 \times 10^{-8}$, $k_3=4.8 \times 10^{-13}$; H_4SiO_4 , $k=2 \times 10^{-10}$) are very high in comparison to that of HCl, the acid liberated remains in the flask and does not come with air. Hence, it seems that antimonite can

Fig. 6. Effect of some salts on Li-H exchange on antimonite at $443 \pm 5 \text{ K}$.

be used for the separation of Li from its minerals, namely spodumene, $\text{LiAlSi}_2\text{O}_6$, amblygonite, LiAlPO_4F etc. Fig. 4 shows that Li-H exchange depends on the particle size and it follows the expression, $\log p = k \cdot \xi$; where p is the mesh size of antimonite, k is the constant, and ξ is the ion-exchange capacity (meq/g) of antimonite. It suggests that the reaction is diffusion-controlled¹³.

Thermodynamic parameters in solid state may offer more clear explanation for the ion-exchange. The absence of solvent precludes such factors as hydration, dilution and mixing and it is the ion-exchange process which takes part in solid state. The positive values of ΔG° indicate that Li^+ has a lower preference for antimonite. The negative values of enthalpy suggest that Li^+ is strongly bonded with antimonite which finds support from the fact that the heat involved in the course of ion-exchange process¹⁴ is usually small, $< 2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Isotherms show that Li-H exchange increases with temperature while the value of enthalpy is negative. The reason for this ambiguity is that the ion-exchange is diffusion-controlled and diffusion increases as the temperature increases. The negative value of ΔS° points out that Li-form of antimonite is more ordered. These results

support the Li-H exchange on antimonite acid in solid state. Therefore, antimonite acid is an important Li selective ion-exchanger.

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